

The Digital Democracy Score (DDS) launched: A Tool for Measuring Digital Democracy

A web-based research-backed tool to assess the level of digital democracy

Brussels, 27 January 2026 – The EU-funded project INNOVADE: Innovative Democracy through Digitalisation (<https://innovade-democracy.eu/>) has released a prototype of a new tool for measuring digital democracy: the Digital Democracy Score (DDS). The DDS is available online in English as a web-based tool at: <https://www.digital-democracy.net>

The tool uses survey questions to calculate a series of digital democracy scores, visualises the results, and provides tailored recommendations. The DDS is designed as a support tool for anyone who uses or operates digital democracy technologies, from local to national and transnational contexts.

Wide-Ranging Applications

The DDS offers valuable insights for a diverse range of users, including operators of political online discussion forums; neighbourhood groups organising online citizen engagement; local communities and cities running citizen reporting systems such as FixMyStreet or digital participatory budgeting platforms like Decidim, Consul, or DemocracyOS; organisations using decision-making or opinion-mapping software such as Loomio or Pol.is; parliaments and civil society organisations offering civic technologies such as online petition systems; local, regional, or national governments using e-voting; and governments and communities using digital media to support citizens' assemblies and citizens' councils.

Measuring Multiple Dimensions of Digital Democracy

Paderborn University's research team that consists of Kevin Friesch, Christian Fuchs, and Joel Musba, developed the DDS. Professor Christian Fuchs, who led the development of the DDS, commented:

“There is not one single digital democracy. There are different forms and models of digital democracy. The Digital Democracy Score takes this diversity into account. It is highly flexible and well suited to measuring different varieties of digital democracy. The tool calculates up to six distinct scores and combines them into one overall score: the Digital Democracy Score.”

By focusing on different dimensions of digital democracy, the DDS can calculate the following scores: the Constitutional Digital Democracy Score (CODDI), Deliberative Digital Democracy Score (DEDDI), Participatory Digital Democracy Score (PADDI), Representative Digital Democracy Score (REDDI), Direct Digital Democracy Score (DIDDI), and Pluralist Digital Democracy Score (PLUDDI).

Depending on the functionalities of the digital democracy initiative being assessed, the tool calculates some or all of these scores and combines them into an overall Digital Democracy Score (DDS) ranging from 0 (very low) to 100 (very high).

Free Training Workshops

The INNOVADE project will host two free online training workshops to introduce and explain the DDS:

- **Tuesday, 24 February 2026, 10:00 CET - 11:00 CET**
- **Wednesday, 4 March 2026, 10:00 CET - 11:00 CET**

Registration is available at: <https://bit.ly/digds>

Participation in the training workshop, access to and use of the DDS tool are completely free of charge.

INNOVADE project

INNOVADE (INNOVative DEMocracy through digitalisation) <https://innovade-democracy.eu/> is a 36-month Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action running from 1 January 2025 to 31 December 2027. The project responds to the challenges and risks brought by digital platforms to democratic life and aims to deliver advanced tools and frameworks that enable inclusive, transparent, and effective e-participation across Europe. Building on existing knowledge and analysing emerging trends, INNOVADE develops scalable and replicable solutions to foster a digitally enhanced public sphere and strengthen democratic governance. A key feature of the project is its Living Labs methodology and pilots. INNOVADE ensures that its outputs address real community needs and result in practical, user-friendly applications that empower citizens to engage with government and influence decisions that shape their lives.

Get Involved

Policymakers, institutions, civil society organisations, and citizens are invited to engage with INNOVADE.

To stay updated on INNOVADE's progress, register for the newsletter at: <https://innovade-democracy.eu/newsletter>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovade-democracy>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@innovade-democracy>

Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/innovade/>

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/innovade-democracy.bsky.social>

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